

1 Supplementary Table S1. Sampling, genotyping, and harmonic mean N_E information per sample. Default filters were minimum depth of coverage
 2 of 6, a maximum depth of coverage of 50, the removal of indels, and to remove sites with more than two alleles.

Sample	SRA #	Species	Common Name	HWI	Locality	Lat.	Long.	Elevation	Mbp Sequenced	Raw Reads	Mapped Reads	Ref Genome Mean Coverage	Proportion Reads Mapped	Sites Genotyped After Filtering	Observed Heterozygosity (x 100)	Harmonic Mean N_E (x 1000)
EB008	SRX7691384	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	10.95	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	35446	234742002	212313525	17.78	0.90	864545653	0.5142	232
EB009	SRX7691385	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	11.71	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	36734	243275606	219841395	18.35	0.90	867966935	0.5123	228
EB024	SRX7691396	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	12.52	Katcha	6.717	39.725	2384	40710	269605526	240590042	20.27	0.89	869491055	0.5135	239
EB044	SRX7691407	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	15.31	Menagesha	8.966	38.563	2851	36116	239184590	215079297	18.09	0.90	866947209	0.5294	260
EB062	SRX7691408	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	10.56	Menagesha	8.967	38.572	2936	47629	315430244	273354530	22.10	0.87	876531309	0.5380	270
EB069	SRR23959152	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	11.10	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	47453	314260840	277777448	23.27	0.88	878415843	0.5156	229
EB085	SRR23959151	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	12.85	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	42160	279211160	248315152	20.31	0.89	875141553	0.5098	223
EB087	SRR23959144	<i>Cossypha semirufa</i>	Ruppell's Robin-chat	12.35	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	36932	244588318	217330972	17.70	0.89	860118114	0.4825	201
EB007	SRX7691390	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	12.07	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	44998	298002828	263490546	25.86	0.88	873754255	0.2421	65
EB015	SRX7691391	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	14.46	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	40731	269746716	242065591	23.91	0.90	883382496	0.2324	63
EB043	SRX7691392	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	13.09	Menagesha	8.966	38.563	2851	32770	217021954	192799492	18.82	0.89	889177322	0.3593	212
EB058	SRX7691393	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	14.83	Menagesha	8.967	38.572	2936	36007	238457506	214757377	21.17	0.90	733656024	0.3596	219
EB064	SRX7691394	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	14.89	Menagesha	8.967	38.572	2936	50377	333627124	291328958	28.34	0.87	915412451	0.3767	221
EB086	SRR23959143	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	15.12	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	44409	294103360	255200510	24.82	0.87	915429129	0.3678	206
EB092	SRR23959142	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	12.78	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	43737	289650514	256618819	25.09	0.89	915485822	0.3711	218
EB094	SRR23959141	<i>Crihagra tristriata</i>	Brown-rumped Seedeater	13.44	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	36187	239651022	214875086	21.07	0.90	915496248	0.3546	207
EB002	SRX7691409	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	16.70	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	35460	234835948	213537879	18.73	0.91	910922684	0.3248	136
EB003	SRX7691410	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	16.24	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	44924	297511668	266160321	23.24	0.89	910943425	0.3367	136
EB053	SRX7691411	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	14.55	Menagesha	8.967	38.558	2732	43650	289075990	257730903	22.13	0.89	911008657	0.3262	127
EB059	SRX7691412	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	16.00	Menagesha	8.967	38.572	2936	37552	248690400	223401275	19.19	0.90	911019223	0.3205	130
EB063	SRX7691413	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	14.78	Menagesha	8.967	38.572	2936	40821	270341524	238940890	20.69	0.88	911028533	0.3268	132
EB067	SRX7691386	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	16.51	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	45158	299061020	267705363	23.00	0.90	911036151	0.3372	138
EB084	SRR23959140	<i>Melaenornis chocolatinus</i>	Abyssinian Slaty Flycatcher	17.95	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	18759	124233898	112948592	9.29	0.91	911043242	0.2465	119
EB004	SRX7691387	<i>Sylvia galinieri</i>	Abyssinian Catbird	9.75	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	16670	110402124	100349106	8.30	0.91	911048121	0.0997	38
EB017	SRX7691388	<i>Sylvia galinieri</i>	Abyssinian Catbird	11.52	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	21270	140864414	126295779	10.52	0.90	911051707	0.0959	38
EB056	SRX7691389	<i>Sylvia galinieri</i>	Abyssinian Catbird	11.63	Menagesha	8.967	38.572	2936	20721	137230934	122230468	9.67	0.89	911054879	0.0906	39
EB070	SRR23959139	<i>Sylvia galinieri</i>	Abyssinian Catbird	10.88	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	20380	134969378	121525519	9.86	0.90	878375279	0.0867	36
EB073	SRR23959138	<i>Sylvia galinieri</i>	Abyssinian Catbird	10.51	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	21652	143395754	128960111	10.58	0.90	888210108	0.0951	35
EB076	SRR23959137	<i>Sylvia galinieri</i>	Abyssinian Catbird	13.66	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	19511	129218494	113940197	9.21	0.88	883440135	0.1049	37
EB001	SRX7691395	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	22.74	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	16349	108272534	97588426	7.56	0.90	915504286	0.3692	352
EB006	SRX7691397	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	18.05	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	20450	135435226	117608266	9.04	0.87	915512453	0.4339	353
EB010	SRX7691398	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	23.48	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	19639	130060708	113171002	8.46	0.87	915519988	0.4085	349
EB042	SRX7691399	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	17.10	Menagesha	8.966	38.563	2851	18351	121532080	107601190	8.19	0.89	915524690	0.4010	373
EB045	SRX7691400	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	16.33	Menagesha	8.966	38.563	2851	21027	139254604	124471739	9.60	0.89	915527996	0.4430	374
EB046	SRX7691401	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	22.06	Menagesha	8.966	38.563	2851	20413	135190396	119745270	9.01	0.89	699810972	0.4261	372

EB079	SRR23959150	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	18.69	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	18274	121020340	105288453	7.69	0.87	798613514	0.3729	384
EB088	SRR23959149	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	18.65	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	19522	129285918	112724391	8.34	0.87	769398010	0.4029	380
EB093	SRR23959148	<i>Turdus abyssinicus</i>	Abyssinian Thrush	20.95	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	19935	132026018	115505159	8.38	0.87	777625877	0.4026	385
EB013	SRX7691402	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	23.80	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	21203	140423232	123096066	10.34	0.88	759356445	0.2958	162
EB049	SRX7691403	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	21.93	Menagesha	8.967	38.558	2732	43779	289932132	254926884	21.54	0.88	868716957	0.3618	159
EB050	SRX7691404	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	24.77	Menagesha	8.967	38.558	2732	41163	272604690	233966456	19.52	0.86	862990502	0.3557	171
EB051	SRX7691405	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	20.00	Menagesha	8.967	38.558	2732	37659	249400922	215784746	18.25	0.87	858998196	0.3536	171
EB065	SRX7691406	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	25.37	Dinsho	7.095	39.789	3283	44500	294707530	247103114	20.78	0.84	874354068	0.3315	170
EB081	SRR23959147	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	20.74	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	40999	271520958	237620277	20.25	0.88	870954866	0.3317	167
EB089	SRR23959146	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	22.28	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	61843	409558500	340423731	28.71	0.83	888706574	0.3410	163
EB090	SRR23959145	<i>Zosterops poliogastrus</i>	Ethiopian White-eye	18.29	Choke	10.781	37.660	3013	47362	313660382	269962536	22.50	0.86	876839823	0.3349	164

Supplementary Table S2. Dataset filtering regimes and number of markers/sites across analyses following group genotyping. Filters mentioned in the table are additional to the default filters including a minimum average depth of coverage of 6, a maximum average depth of coverage of 50, the removal of indels, and to remove sites with more than two alleles.

Set	Missing Data (%)	MAC ¹	Invar. Sites	OG ²	Window Size	# Windows	SNP Spacing ³	# Sites	# SNPs	Analyses
A	0	2					20Kbp	35,446-49,213	35,446-49,213	STRUCTURE, PCA
B	0	2					10Kbp	62,387-96,569	62,387-96,569	STRUCTURE, PCA
C	20		X	X	50Kbp	21230		865,606,889-940,062,147	6,011,672-19,560,331	RAxML, ASTRAL III
D	0		X					865,606,889-940,062,147	3,393,662-19,980,484	H _o
E	95*		X					865,606,889-940,061,924	6,365,217-37,913,177	MSMC2
F	0							865,648-10,173,419	865,648-10,173,419	F _{ST}

MAC¹: Minor allele frequency

OG²: Outgroup included

SNP Spacing³: Minimum distance between any two SNPs

F_{ST} dataset did not include chromosomes 4A or Z.

* Percent missing data filter to keep sites genotyped in at least one individual during group genotyping. Each individual VCF was additionally filtered to contain no missing genotype information for running MSMC2.

Supplementary Figure S1. Frequency distributions of genomic depth of coverage for each individual.

Supplementary Figure S2. Linear regression of the association between F_{ST} and hand-wing index. a) Great Rift Valley. b) Blue Nile Valley. Row 1: $\log F_{ST}$ explained by intraspecific mean HWI. Row 2: $\log F_{ST}$ PICs explained by mean intraspecific HWI PICs.

Supplementary Figure S3. Linear regression of the association between F_{ST} and H_O for each species. a) Great Rift Valley. b) Blue Nile Valley. Row 1: $\log F_{ST}$ explained by species mean H_O . Row 2: $\log F_{ST}$ PICs explained by species mean H_O PICs.

Supplementary Figure S4. Linear Regression of the association between F_{ST} and species' elevational occurrence range calculated as the maximum elevational occurrence minus the minimum elevational occurrence. a) Great Rift Valley. b) Blue Nile Valley. Row 1: $\log F_{ST}$ explained by species elevational range. Row 2: $\log F_{ST}$ PICs explained by species elevational range PICs.

Supplementary Figure S5. Linear regression between observed heterozygosity (H_o) PICs and harmonic mean N_E PICs per individual.

Supplementary Figure S6. Linear regression of individual H_0 on individual mean depth of coverage. Coefficient of determination and p value for *T. abyssinicus* displayed near its points.

Supplementary Figure S7. a) Linear regression of Individual Harmonic Mean N_E and Individual Hand-wing Index (HWI) and b) Linear regression of Individual Harmonic Mean N_E PICs on Individual HWI PICs.

Supplementary Figure S8. Individual N_E trajectories per species from MSMC2 analysis.

Supplementary Figure S9. a) Linear regression of Individual H_0 on Hand-wing Index (HWI) and b) Linear regression of Individual H_0 PICs on Hand-wing Index PICs.

